

UPDATE ON THE LUNAR-VISE INVESTIGATION OF MONS GRUITHUISEN GAMMA. K. L. Donaldson Hanna¹, J. Benavente¹, K. Bennett², B. Denevi³, A. Dove¹, J. Hagerty⁴, C. Hardgrove⁵, P. Hayne⁶, L. Heffern⁷, A. LaMee¹, M. E. Landis⁵, T. Prettyman⁸, J. V. Rudd⁹, R. N. Schindhelm⁹, K. A. Shirley¹⁰, M. Siegler¹¹, J. Sunshine¹², P. Tripathi¹, J-P. Williams¹³, S. Valencia¹², BAE team⁹, and Arizona State University team⁵, ¹University of Central Florida (Kerri.DonaldsonHanna@ucf.edu), ²Northern Arizona University, ³Johns Hopkins Applied Physics Laboratory, ⁴U.S. Geological Survey, ⁵Arizona State University, ⁶University of Colorado Boulder, ⁷AstraNext, ⁸Planetary Science Institute, ⁹BAE Systems, ¹⁰University of Oxford, ¹¹University of Hawaii, ¹²University of Maryland, ¹³University of California Los Angeles.

Introduction: The Gruithuisen domes (36°N, 40°W) were first identified as volcanic structures distinct from their surrounding mare flows based on their morphology and unusually red-sloped UV-visible spectrum [e.g., 1–3]. Morphologic analyses of the steep-sided domes suggested they are composed of highly viscous magmas similar to terrestrial extrusive volcanic features, which are consistent with higher silica contents (> 52 wt.% SiO₂) found in rhyolites, dacites and basaltic andesites [e.g., 4]. Further observations by Lunar Prospector (LP), Diviner Lunar Radiometer (Diviner), and the Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter Camera (LROC) have shown that the domes are enriched in Th (~17 to 40 ppm) and SiO₂, and low in FeO [e.g., 5–7]. However, the exact composition of the rock making up the domes has remained elusive. In particular, Diviner’s compositional bands were not optimized for constraining the composition of highly silicic materials [6,8], making it challenging to constrain how such rocks could form on a single plate planetary body like the Moon.

Mission Objectives: The Lunar Vulkan Imaging and Spectroscopy Explorer (Lunar-VISE) instrument suite was selected through NASA’s Payloads and Research Investigations on the Surface of the Moon (PRISM) program and will be deployed on the Moon by Firefly Aerospace, which was selected through NASA’s Commercial Lunar Payload Services (CLPS) program for task order CP-21. Lunar-VISE will land on Mons Gruithuisen Gamma (hereafter referred to informally as “the Gamma dome”) and will use its combined lander and rover payload to determine the composition and physical properties of the rocks and regolith comprising the domes, placing critical constraints on their formation mechanism.

The overarching science goal of the Lunar-VISE investigation is to understand how late-stage silicic volcanism works under lunar conditions, as typified by the Gruithuisen domes. This goal will be accomplished through two science objectives that place critical constraints on the main hypotheses for the formation of non-mare silicic volcanic constructs by (1) mapping spatial variations in composition along the notional rover traverse, and correlating the measured variations to rock and regolith properties, surface features, and dome morphology. Lunar-VISE will also (2) relate those local-scale measurements to orbital remote sensing observations from previous

and current spacecraft. Our primary exploration goal is to understand the geotechnical properties of the lunar regolith on the domes at the lander/rover scale. This exploration goal will be accomplished by mapping local variations in regolith properties of the region surrounding the landing site and along the rover’s traverse.

Figure 1. (top) LROC WAC albedo map of the Gruithuisen Domes with the LOLA slope map overlain. The green box highlights the area of the Lunar-VISE landing site. **(bottom)** Lunar-VISE landing site and notional rover traverse with stations identified where LV-VIMS and LV-GRNS measurements will be made. Mareta crater (150 m diameter crater, 40.81°E, 36.45°N) shown in the lower left.

Lunar-VISE Instrument Suite: To achieve our goals and objectives, Lunar-VISE includes a

complementary suite of heritage instruments on a rover and lander. The rover payload includes two separate units, the Lunar-VISE Visible/Infrared Multiband Suite (LV-VIMS) and the Gamma-Ray and Neutron Spectrometer (LV-GRNS).

LV-VIMS is an instrument suite combining two multispectral imaging instruments in a single enclosure: the VNIR Imaging Camera (LV-VIC) and the Compact Infrared Imaging System (LV-CIRiS). From their location on top of the rover, these multispectral cameras image the landscape in panoramic scans up to 180°. The LV-VIC and LV-CIRiS cameras are co-boresighted and rotate together on a common stage. LV-VIC draws heritage from BAE's GeoSpace Camera (BGSC), a visible camera originally designed for NASA's Orion program [9]. LV-CIRiS draws heritage from BAE's CIRiS instrument, which operated in low Earth orbit for 3 years before being decommissioned in mid-2023, and L-CIRiS built for delivery to the lunar south pole in 2027 on CP-22 [10]. LV-VIC spectral channels were chosen to be at similar wavelengths to those on the Clementine UVVIS, LROC Wide Angle Camera, and Kaguya Multiband Imager. The three compositional channels of LV-CIRiS were specifically chosen to estimate the SiO₂ content of highly silicic regions and are at similar wavelengths as on Diviner and L-CIRiS.

The LV-GRNS is located on the rear of the rover where it acquires measurements of gamma rays and neutrons emitted from the lunar surface, both spanning the energy range needed to quantify critical elements including Si, Fe, and Th [11]. LV-GRNS is a rebuild, with minor modifications, of the Miniature Neutron Spectrometer launched on LunaH-Map in November 2022 [12-13]. The GRNS incorporates two sensor heads each coupled to its own photomultiplier tube (PMT): (1) the gamma ray detector, a cylindrical 2.5" diameter CLYC scintillator crystal; and (2) the thermal and epithermal detector, a cylindrical 2.0" diameter CLYC scintillator crystal [11].

The lander suite includes two cameras for characterizing the landing site and surrounding area, and the rover traverse: the Lunar-VISE Descent Camera (LV-DC) for surface imaging during landing, and the Lunar-VISE Context Camera (LV-CC) for panoramas up to 270° around the landing site and the rover traverse. Both cameras are similar to LV-VIC but without the multispectral capabilities.

Landing Site and Notional Design Reference

Mission: The Lunar-VISE team evaluated several candidate landing sites based on how each met critical and strongly desired criteria including access to boulders and possible exposure of bedrock within a crater, access to the dome edge providing a view of the surrounding maria and Delta dome, a relatively flat (< 5° slopes) area with a terrain ruggedness index (TRI) < 0.4 that could accommodate a 100-m diameter circular landing ellipse, favorable

illumination conditions to maximize mission duration, and traverse options that maintained line-of-sight communication between the rover and lander [14]. Our chosen landing ellipse is centered at 40.797°E, 36.457°N (**Figure 1**), which is near the edge of a topographic step near the top of the Gamma dome that provides a relatively flat area for landing, a view off the dome with a short (~50 – 150 m) rover traverse, and abundant access to a field of boulders excavated by Mareta crater (**Figure 1**).

Current Mission Status: Instrument integration and environmental testing of the Lunar-VISE instruments are currently being completed with the Lunar-VISE system integration review (SIR) and delivery in place (DIP) scheduled for spring 2026. The Lunar-VISE team has continued to work with Firefly Aerospace and Blue Origin/Honeybee to deliver instruments for integration onto the lander and rover in late 2026/early 2027, and to further develop surface operation plans for a landing in 2028.

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References: [1] Head J. W. and McCord T. B. (1978) *Science*, 199, 1433-1436. [2] Bruno B. C. et al. (1991) *LPSC XXI*, 405-415. [3] Chevrel S. D. et al. (1999) *JGR*, 104, 16515-16529. [4] Wilson L. and Head J. W. (2003) *JGR Planets*, 108(E2), 5012. [5] Hagerty J. J. et al. (2006) *JGR*, 111, doi:10.1029/2005JE002592. [6] Glotch T. D. et al. (2010) *Science*, 329, 1510-1513. [7] Clegg-Watkins R. N. (2017) *Icarus*, 285, 169-184. [8] Greenhagen B. T. et al. (2010) *Science*, 329, 1507-1509. [9] Schindhelm R. N. et al. (2025) *56th LPSC*, this conference. [10] Rudd J. V. et al. (2025) *56th LPSC*, this conference. [11] Hardgrove C. et al. (2025) *56th LPSC*, this conference. [12] Hardgrove C. et al. (2020) *IEEE*. [13] Hardgrove C. et al. (2023) *54th LPSC*, Abstract #2960. [14] Williams J.-P. et al. (2024) *55th LPSC*, Abstract #1688.